

INCORPORATION OF TiO₂ NANOPARTICLES IN THIN FILMS DEPOSITED ON AISI 304 STAINLESS STEEL USING THE CATHODIC CAGE TECHNIQUE: A PRELIMINARY STUDY

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ABSTRACT

TiO₂ (titanium dioxide) nanoparticles have been widely used in various industrial sectors, such as photodegradation and photocatalysis systems, photovoltaic cells and biomedical applications, exhibiting osseointegration, bactericidal, antitumor and cell differentiation properties. These nanoparticles can be used in the form of powders, crystals, nanorods, nanotubes and thin films. In this sense, as an alternative to improve the surface properties of AISI 304 stainless steel, TiO₂ nanoparticles (powders) were incorporated into thin films obtained through duplex plasma treatment (conventional plasma nitriding followed by cathodic cage plasma deposition) in order to evaluate the mechanical properties, wettability and bacterial response. The thin films were characterized using Grazing Incidence X-Ray Diffraction (GIXRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS), and Rockwell C adhesion, Vickers microhardness, surface roughness (Ra and Rg), wettability and bacterial adhesion tests. The treatment was efficient in depositing

coatings incorporating TiO₂ nanoparticles on the surface of AISI 304 steel, obtaining thin films with good layer uniformity and excellent adhesion to the substrate. All the treated samples had a higher surface microhardness than the untreated sample. After the treatments, the films showed an increase in surface roughness which corroborated in obtaining more hydrophilic surfaces, with contact angle reductions of up to 88.94%, and lower bacterial adhesion activity, showing reductions of up to 78.42%. The set of attractive and promising properties obtained with the deposition of these films may arouse interest in their use in biomedical applications, such as their possible use in metal prostheses.

KEYWORDS: AISI 304; TiO₂ Nanoparticles; Cathodic Cage Plasma Deposition; Mechanical Properties; Bacterial Response.

I. INTRODUCTION

TiO₂ (titanium dioxide) nanoparticles can be found in the form of powders [1], crystals [2], nanoblasts [3], nanotubes [4] and thin films [5]. In terms of crystal structure, there are three crystallographic forms: rutile (tetragonal), brookite (orthorhombic) and anatase (tetragonal) [6], whose phase transformation can be induced by heat treatment [7]. The commercial and technological importance of TiO₂ nanoparticles is attributed to their valuable properties, such as their use in photodegradation and photocatalysis systems, photovoltaic cells, electrochemical sensors, biological applications exhibiting characteristics of osseointegration, bactericide, antitumor agent and cell differentiation [8], [9], [10].

Several methods including sol-gel processes [11], [12], electrophoretic deposition [7], [13], chemical vapor deposition [14], [15], [16] and physical vapor deposition [17], [18], [19] have been used to obtain TiO₂-based thin films on different types of substrates. Among the PVD processes, the Cathodic Cage Plasma Deposition (CCPD) technique has emerged as an efficient method for depositing thin films of different chemical compositions on various types of substrates, with good layer uniformity, higher deposition rates and lower treatment temperatures when compared to CVD processes.

De Sousa et al., (2015) [20] deposited thin films of titanium nitride (TiN) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) on silicon substrates using the CCPD technique and investigated the influence of temperature and treatment atmosphere on the chemical, structural and morphological characteristics of the films. A similar study by Sousa et al., (2015) [21], investigated the influence of temperature, treatment time and gas atmosphere on the structural, morphological and chemical characteristics of TiN and TiO₂ thin films deposited using the CCPD technique on glass substrates. Lopes et al., (2018) [22] deposited TiO₂ thin films by the CCPD method on duplex stainless steel substrates in order to investigate the influence of varying treatment parameters, atmosphere and treatment time, on the structural properties and corrosion resistance of the deposited thin films.

Although it is possible to find works using the CCPD technique to deposit TiO₂ thin films, in all cases the authors used a titanium cathodic cage configuration (as a target) in an oxygen-containing atmosphere. However, the incorporation of TiO₂ nanoparticles in the form of targets inserted into the cage, i.e. modifying the cathodic cage plasma deposition technique and keeping the treatment atmosphere in the presence of inert gases in order to induce the sputtering mechanism to act preferentially on the TiO₂ targets, has not yet been reported in the literature. This new cathodic cage arrangement was based on the study by Neto et al., (2024) [23].

In this context, this preliminary study aims to evaluate the mechanical properties, wettability and bacterial response of thin films containing TiO₂ nanoparticles deposited on AISI 304 austenitic stainless steel by modifying the conventional cathodic cage plasma deposition technique by inserting targets made with the nanoparticles in powder form, for potential use as a coating for biomedical applications such as the coating of metal prostheses.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

This work used samples of AISI 304 stainless steel (chemical composition: 19.00% wt. Cr, 10.00% wt. Ni, 0.03% wt. C and % wt. Fe in balance) with dimensions of 19 mm in diameter and 8 mm thick, supplied by Villares Metals. To carry out the treatments, the samples underwent metallographic

procedures consisting of grinding, polishing, cleaning in an acetone solution with ultrasonic agitation for 10 minutes and drying.

An AISI 316 stainless steel cathodic cage was used (chemical composition: 16.00%wt. Cr, 10.00% wt. Ni, 0.08%wt. C, 2.00%wt. Mn, 2.50%wt. Mo and %wt. Fe in balance) with dimensions of 70 mm in diameter, 42 mm in height, 2 mm thick, with holes 8 mm in diameter and 9 mm between the centers of adjacent holes. Before treatment, the cage was also subjected to the following steps: grinding, cleaning with an acetone solution under ultrasonic agitation for 10 minutes and drying.

The TiO₂ nanoparticles used to produce the targets were synthesized according to the methodology adopted in Carvalho Naves et al., (2018) [24]. After obtaining the nanoparticles, they were divided into three parts, one of which was subjected to heat treatment at 500 °C, the other at 650 °C and the last at 800 °C, all lasting one hour. Next, to form the targets, each of the three types of TiO₂ nanoparticle underwent a compaction stage in a hydraulic press with a load of 2 tons in order to acquire the shape of a ring with an internal diameter of 8 mm and an external diameter of 11.8 mm. For each type of nanoparticle, 19 targets were obtained and inserted into the holes in the lid of the cathodic cage, as shown in Figure 1(b). The procedure for making the targets was based on Neto et al., (2024) [23].

2.2. Treatment parameters

The first stage of the treatment was conventional plasma nitriding, Figure 1(a), where the sample remains at cathodic potential when positioned directly on the sample holder. The second stage was cathodic cage plasma deposition, Figure 1(b), where the sample is positioned on the alumina, thus remaining at floating potential so that the sputtering mechanism is directed only at the cage and, consequently, at the TiO₂ nanoparticle targets which are positioned in the holes of the cathodic cage lid.

Figure 1 - Schematic representation of the (a) conventional plasma nitriding and (b) cathodic cage plasma deposition processes used to obtain thin films on an AISI 304 steel substrate.

The treatments were preceded by a pre-sputtering step for preliminary cleaning. For this work, this stage was carried out in an atmosphere composed of 30 sccm of H₂ and 30 sccm of Ar at 300 °C for one hour. The nomenclature of the samples and the treatment parameters used in each stage are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Sample nomenclature and treatment parameters adopted for film deposition.

Sample	Conventional plasma nitriding			Cathodic cage plasma deposition		
	Temperature	Time	Gases	Temperature	Time	Gases
UT	-					
TiO ₂ _500	400 (°C)	4 (h)	80 H ₂ / 8 N ₂ (sccm)	400 (°C)	4 (h)	30 Ar (sccm)
TiO ₂ _650						
TiO ₂ _800						

2.3. Characterization techniques and tests

The grazing incidence X-ray diffraction technique was employed to identify the phases present after film deposition. A Shimadzu diffractometer (model DRX-7000) with a grazing incidence angle of 1°, CuK α radiation source, operated at a current of 40 mA, voltage of 40 kV, and a 2 θ scanning range from 20° to 80° was used for the analyses. The phases were identified with the aid of COD (Crystallography Open Database) and ICDD (International Centre for Diffraction Data) databases.

The surface morphology and cross-sectional measurements of the films were analyzed using the Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) technique, using a FEI Company scanning electron microscope (model Quanta FEG 250). To analyze the cross-section, the samples were chemically attacked by immersing them in Marble solution (4 g CuSO₄ + 20 ml HCl + 20 ml H₂O) for approximately 10 seconds. The elemental composition of the films was evaluated by Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) using Bruker equipment (Quantax EDS model) with XFlash 5010 detector.

The adhesion criteria were assessed using the Rockwell C adhesion test based on the Daimler-Benz VDI 3198 standard [25], using an Insize durometer (model ISH-BRV). Images of the indentations were obtained using a BEL Photonics optical microscope (model MTM-1A).

The Vickers microhardness test was carried out using an Insize microhardness tester (model ISH-TDV 1000), and the tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM standard E92-17 [26]. For each sample, 5 indentations were made using a load of 0.05 kgf with an indentation time of 15 s. The mean and standard deviation values of the measurements were considered for analysis.

Surface roughness analysis was carried out based on the ISO 21920-2:2021 standard, using a Mitutoyo portable roughness meter (model SJ-210). Measurements were made using the R profile setting, Gaussian filter, cutoff λ_c of 0.8 mm, cutoff λ_s of 2.5 μ m and a measuring speed of 0.5 mm/s. For analysis purposes, five measurements were taken on each sample, resulting in the mean and standard deviation of the roughness parameters Ra and Rq.

The apparatus used to analyze the wettability properties of the samples consisted of a support and a high-resolution digital camera positioned in front of the sample. To carry out the test, three samples were used for each treatment condition and three measurements were taken on each one, the result being the mean and standard deviation. Each sample was positioned horizontally on the support and a drop of 2 μ L of distilled water was placed on it using a vertical pipette. The contact angle formed between the drop of water and the surface of the sample indicates whether the surface has hydrophilic or hydrophobic potential. The “Surftens” software was used to measure the contact angles of each sample.

For the biological test involving bacteria, the ESBL-resistant *Escherichia coli* strain was sourced from the microorganism collection at the Medical Bacteriology Laboratory (LaBMed) at the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte. The bacterial cells were plated on Mueller Hinton agar and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours to allow for growth. Multiple colonies were then collected to create a bacterial suspension in sterile 0.9% sodium chloride, adjusting the optical density to 0.73 ± 0.005 (equivalent to 1 McFarland) by repeating a few colonies in saline, homogenizing, and measuring 200 μ L at OD600 nm in a 96-well plate. To assess strain viability, the crystal violet method was employed. In triplicate, 400 μ L of the bacterial suspension and 600 μ L of Brain Heart Infusion Broth

(BHI) were added to each well of 12-well plates. The plates were incubated at 36 °C for 24 hours. Following incubation, the medium was discarded, and 1000 μ L of 0.4% Crystal Violet was added for 15 minutes. After removing the Crystal Violet, the wells were washed with running water until no dye was visible. Subsequently, 1000 μ L of 99.5% DMSO was added to each well and allowed to sit for 30 minutes. Finally, 200 μ L from each well was transferred to a 96-well plate for measurement using a Spectramax at 570 nm.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. XRD analysis

The XRD patterns of the untreated sample (UT) and the samples after the first stage of duplex treatment, conventional plasma nitriding, can be seen in Figure 2. The position of the peaks recorded for the untreated sample agrees with the patterns published for 304 austenitic stainless steel in the ICDD [27], with the presence of an additional peak at 44.5° which suggests the presence of a chromium phase [28]. The diffractograms indicate a structural change in the surface after conventional plasma nitriding, indicated by the presence of peaks at 41.05°, 47.01° and 70.27° associated with the Fe₄N-type iron nitride phase (COD - 9004225), and a peak at 43.72° suggesting the presence of Fe₃N-type iron nitride (COD - 2310869).

Figure 2 - XRD patterns of the untreated sample and after conventional plasma nitriding treatment.

The XRD patterns obtained for the samples after the second stage of duplex treatment, Figure 3, show new structural changes for the three conditions studied. It is possible to notice differences in the predominance of the titanium oxide phases presented according to the processing temperature of the TiO₂ targets. For the TiO₂_500 sample, a clearer presence of the rutile phase can be seen (COD - 90004142). As the target processing temperature increases, the XRD patterns suggest a decrease in the presence of this phase and the appearance of the brookite (COD - 8104269) and anatase (COD - 9008216) phases for the TiO₂_650 sample. For the TiO₂_800 sample, the patterns only suggest the presence of the brookite (COD - 8104269) and rutile (COD - 90004142) phases, with an even greater decrease in the presence of the latter. The presence of titanium oxide phases on the surface of the

treated samples shows the efficiency of the film deposition technique. The XRD results also indicate the possibility of obtaining films with different TiO₂ phases, the nature and proportion of which can be controlled by varying the processing temperature of the TiO₂ targets.

Figure 3 - XRD patterns of samples treated by duplex plasma treatment (conventional plasma nitriding followed by cathodic cage plasma deposition).

In addition, peaks of the iron oxide phases Fe₂O₃ (COD - 1011240) and Fe₃O₄ (COD - 1010369) were observed in the treated samples. These phases, considered undesirable from the point of view of using the films in biomedical applications, are justified by the fact that during the plasma deposition treatment with a cathodic cage, the sputtering not only acts on the TiO₂ targets positioned in the holes of the lid, but also concentrates on the holes of the cage cylinder, causing iron atoms to be ejected from the 316 steel cage and possibly combine with the oxygen present on the surface of the samples. As an alternative to avoid the possible formation of these oxides, we can suggest inserting new TiO₂ targets, in addition to those used in the lid, in each hole of the cathodic cage cylinder in order to enhance the effect of sputtering on the targets; another way could be to modify the current arrangement by replacing the cathodic cage material, replacing the AISI 316 steel cage with a titanium cathodic cage.

3.2. SEM and EDS analysis

The SEM micrographs and EDS mapping (titanium and oxygen elements) of the thin films deposited by duplex treatment are shown in Figure 4. The films obtained for the TiO₂_500 and TiO₂_650

samples respectively, Figure 4(a) and 4(b), show similar morphology. On the other hand, on the surface of the TiO₂_800 sample, Figure 4(c), it is possible to observe the preferential growth of the film in the pin-holes characteristic of the processing of AISI 304 stainless steel. EDS mapping shows a good distribution of titanium and oxygen on the surface of the treated samples, suggesting the formation of TiO₂ films, as observed in the XRD patterns in Figure 3.

Figure 4 - SEM micrographs (backscattered electrons) and EDS maps (distribution of Ti and O elements) of the surface morphology of the deposited thin films: (a) TiO₂_500, (b) TiO₂_650 and (c) TiO₂_800.

Figure 5 shows the micrographs obtained by SEM of the cross-section of the samples. It is possible to observe a good uniformity of the deposited films for all the samples, which is reinforced by the low standard deviation values obtained for the thickness of the films. This behavior shows that adding targets to the holes of the cathodic cage maintains the uniformity of the films obtained by cathodic cage plasma deposition [29], [30]. It was also observed that the thickness of the layer increased with the increase in the heat treatment temperature determined for each of the three types of TiO₂ nanoparticles.

Figure 5 - SEM micrographs of the cross-section of the treated samples showing the thickness of the deposited films: (a) TiO₂_500, (b) TiO₂_650 and (c) TiO₂_800.

3.3. Rockwell C adhesion

The adhesion criteria were based on the VDI 3198 standard [25]. From the SEM micrographs of the indentations made in the test, Figure 6, it is not possible to observe the presence of cracks or regions of apparent delamination circumferentially to the indentation, for any of the three treated samples, which allows them to be classified with the best level of film adhesion, HF1.

Figure 6 - Indentations obtained after the Rockwell C adhesion test: (a) TiO₂_500, (b) TiO₂_650 and (c) TiO₂_800.

The excellent behavior of the samples in the adhesion test can be related to the nature of the duplex treatment carried out, since the preliminary conventional plasma nitriding treatment, due to the

hardness gradient formed from the surface to the core, improves the adhesion of the layer deposited in the subsequent treatment, thus helping to prevent the films from detaching [31].

3.4. Vickers microhardness

Figure 7 shows the surface microhardness results for the treated and untreated samples. After the treatments, it was observed that all the treated samples had a higher average surface microhardness than the untreated sample, with the average value for the TiO₂_500 sample being more than twice that of the untreated sample. A direct comparison between the treated samples shows equivalent results, which suggests that the processing temperature of the targets did not significantly influence the microhardness results. This behavior may also be related to the influence of the nitriding stage on the result, so that the values presented do not correspond only to the hardness of the film but to a composite hardness (nitrided layer + deposited film). The gain in microhardness of the treated samples may be related to the presence of the Fe₃N and Fe₄N phases obtained in the first stage of the duplex treatment, conventional plasma nitriding. These phases are well known for conferring high surface hardness [32], [33].

Figure 7 - Vickers microhardness measurements of the untreated and treated samples.

3.5. Surface roughness

Figure 8 shows the surface roughness results of the untreated sample and the treated samples. It can be seen that the treated samples had higher surface roughness values compared to the untreated sample. This behavior is to be expected, as the sputtering carried out in the first stage of treatment, conventional plasma nitriding, acts directly on the samples, contributing to the appearance of surface defects [34].

Among the treated samples, the TiO₂_500 sample showed the highest surface roughness values. The TiO₂_650 and TiO₂_800 samples showed similar behavior in terms of roughness. Increasing surface roughness helps to obtain more hydrophilic surfaces by retaining water in the surface asperities and also helps to reduce bacterial adhesion [35], [36].

Figure 8 - Measurements of the surface roughness parameters Ra and Rq of the untreated and treated samples.

3.6. Wettability

The wettability of the untreated and treated samples was analyzed based on the contact angle formed between the water droplet and the surface, and the results are shown in Figure 9. The decrease in contact angle values can be clearly seen after the duplex treatments. In other words, the thin films obtained showed a greater degree of hydrophilicity than the untreated sample, with contact angles ranging from 6.6° (sample TiO2_650) to 16.1° (sample TiO2_500), respectively, reductions of 88.94% to 73.02%.

Figure 9 - Contact angle measurements of untreated and treated samples.

The more hydrophilic surfaces obtained with the treated samples contribute to less bacterial interaction, i.e. less bacterial adhesion. Previous studies have shown that surfaces with greater hydrophobicity are preferentially attacked by bacteria due to the high adhesion force between the bacteria and the hydrophobic surface, compared to hydrophilic surfaces [37], [38], [39].

3.7. Bacterial adhesion

The results of bacterial adhesion (*E. coli*) after a 24-hour incubation period of the untreated and treated samples are shown in Figure 10. The crystal violet test was used to assess bacterial adhesion based on the relative density of the cells adhered to the surface of the samples analyzed. The treated samples showed lower bacterial adhesion compared to the untreated sample, with reductions of 78.42% to 62.32%, respectively, obtained for the TiO₂_500 and TiO₂_650 samples. These results show that even with the presence of impurities associated with the iron oxide phases on the surface of the coated samples, the deposited films behaved positively in mitigating bacterial adhesion on the surface of AISI 304 stainless steel and also reinforces the application potential of the deposition techniques used.

Figure 10 - Bacterial adhesion measurements (*E. Coli*) of the untreated and treated samples.

An important correlation to be made concerns the influence of surface roughness on bacterial adhesion. Previous studies have reported that there are considerable reductions in bacterial adhesion on rougher surfaces, making them unfavorable for bacterial growth and colonization [36]. This behavior is in line with the results obtained in the present study, where it can be seen that the surface with the highest roughness for the TiO₂_500 sample film was the one that showed the least bacterial colonization, while the surface with the lowest roughness shown by the untreated sample was the one that resulted in the highest rate of bacterial adhesion. Furthermore, the equivalence of the surface roughness results between the TiO₂_650 and TiO₂_800 samples is also observed in the bacterial adhesion results, thus suggesting that there is a strong relationship between surface roughness and bacterial adhesion.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, TiO₂ nanoparticles were incorporated into thin films deposited on AISI 304 austenitic stainless steel substrates using the cathodic cage plasma deposition technique in order to evaluate the mechanical properties and bacterial adhesion response of the coatings obtained. The main conclusions of this study are summarized below:

- The structural change of the surface of AISI 304 stainless steel through the incorporation of TiO₂ nanoparticles into the deposited thin films was efficiently achieved using the cathodic cage plasma deposition technique;

- The films obtained showed good regularity in terms of layer thickness and optimum adhesion conditions to the substrate;
- All the treatments resulted in an increase in surface microhardness, the behavior of which is related to the presence of iron nitride phases of the Fe₃N and Fe₄N types formed during the initial stage of treatment, conventional plasma nitriding;
- There was an increase in surface roughness for all the coated samples compared to the untreated sample. This behavior corroborated the achievement of more hydrophilic surfaces with a lower tendency to bacterial adhesion;
- As a preliminary study, in order for these attractive and promising properties of the films obtained to actually be present as a potential coating for biomedical applications such as use in metal prostheses, the undesirable iron oxide phases identified must be eliminated. To this end, possible solutions to avoid the formation of these impurities could include inserting new targets, in addition to those present in the lid, into each hole of the cathodic cage cylinder or replacing the 316 stainless steel cage with a titanium cage in the arrangement used in this work.

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